

**ФУНДАМЕНТАЛ ВА
КЛИНИК ТИББИЁТ
АХБОРОТНОМАСИ**

**BULLETIN OF FUNDAMENTAL
AND CLINIC MEDICINE**

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КЛИНИЧЕСКОЙ МЕДИЦИНЫ**

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IMPROVEMENT OF METHODS FOR THE CORRECTION OF SMALL INTESTINAL MORPHOLOGY IN A MODEL OF METABOLIC SYNDROME**Dustova G.K., Boykuziyev X.X.**

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Resume. This article presents the improvement of correction methods applied to experimental animals with an induced model of metabolic syndrome. The findings demonstrate a positive dynamic of morphological and functional changes in the wall of the small intestine. Furthermore, the applied correction approach contributed to the overall recovery of the organism and promoted the restoration of the morphological and functional state of the small intestinal wall.

Keywords: metabolic syndrome, alimentary obesity, correction methods

**МЕТАБОЛИК СИНДРОМ МОДЕЛИ АСОСИДА ИНГИЧКА ИЧАК МОРФОЛОГИЯСИНИ
КОРРЕКЦИЯ ҚИЛИШ УСУЛЛАРИНИ ТАКОМИЛЛАШТИРИШ****Дустова Г.К., Бойкузиев Х.Х.**

Самарқанд давлат тиббиёт университети, Самарқанд ш., Ўзбекистон

Резюме. Мазкур мақолада метаболик синдром модели яратилиб, тажриба ҳайвонларида қўлланган коррекция усулларини такомиллаштириши натижалари келтирилган. Тадқиқот натижалари ингичка ичак деворида морфологик ва функционал ўзгаришларнинг ижобий динамикасини кўрсатди. Шу билан бирга, қўлланган коррекция ёндашуви организмнинг умумий соғломлашувига ҳисса қўшди ва ингичка ичак деворининг морфологик ҳамда функционал ҳолатини тиклашга ёрдам берди.

Калит сўзлар: метаболик синдром, алиментар семизлик, коррекция усуллари

**СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЕ МЕТОДОВ КОРРЕКЦИИ МОРФОЛОГИИ ТОНКОЙ КИШКИ НА
МОДЕЛИ МЕТАБОЛИЧЕСКОГО СИНДРОМА****Дустова Г.К., Бойкузиев Х.Х.**

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Резюме. В данной статье представлены усовершенствованные методы коррекции, применяемые к экспериментальным животным с индуцированной моделью метаболического синдрома. Результаты исследования демонстрируют положительную динамику морфологических и функциональных изменений в стенке тонкой кишки. Кроме того, применяемый метод коррекции способствовал общему восстановлению организма и восстановлению морфологического и функционального состояния стенки тонкой кишки.

Ключевые слова: метаболический синдром, алиментарное ожирение, методы коррекции

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Introduction. All components of metabolic syndrome are chronic in nature and typically develop asymptotically in the early stages. As a result, patients often seek medical attention at relatively late stages, which significantly complicates timely diagnosis, prevention, and treatment. Moreover, due to the insufficient understanding of the complex pathophysiological mechanisms underlying metabolic syndrome, a unified and effective system for its correction has not yet been established.

Experts from the World Health Organization (WHO), operating under the United Nations (UN), have characterized metabolic syndrome as a “pandemic of the 21st century,” emphasizing that modern society is facing a new global health challenge affecting populations, particularly in highly industrialized countries. This characterization highlights the critical importance of the issue and places significant responsibility on healthcare professionals and society as a whole. Furthermore, this condition also poses a potential demographic threat to developing countries. Thus, metabolic syndrome and its associated complications remain unresolved medico-social problems worldwide. Addressing this issue requires a deeper understanding of the etiological factors and the underlying mechanisms of disease development.

A number of researchers, including Santos Lacerda D. et al. (2018), conducted experimental studies in which one group of animals was fed a fructose-rich diet, while another group received black grape juice over

a three-month period. The results demonstrated that animals consuming high amounts of fructose developed abdominal obesity and signs of metabolic syndrome. In contrast, animals receiving black grape juice exhibited a reduction in body weight. Based on these findings, the authors concluded that the inclusion of black grapes or their juice in the daily diet may serve as a natural preventive strategy against metabolic syndrome and its complications. This effect is attributed to the presence of proanthocyanidins in black grapes, which possess strong antioxidant properties, neutralize free radicals, reduce blood cholesterol levels, enhance insulin secretion, and contribute to the prevention of cardiovascular diseases, inflammatory conditions, neoplasms, and diabetes mellitus.

The aim of the study The aim of this study was to experimentally investigate the morphology of the small intestinal wall in laboratory animals during the correction of a metabolic syndrome model, developed on the background of alimentary obesity, using black grape juice.

Material and methods. The experimental study was conducted on 42 white outbred male rats aged 8 weeks, with a body weight of 80–100 g. All animals were maintained under standard vivarium conditions at a constant temperature, with a 12-hour light/dark cycle and free access to food and water. The duration of the experiment was 24 weeks.

The animals were divided into three groups. The control group (n = 18) was fed a standard laboratory diet with an energy value of 3000 kcal/kg. The experimental group (n = 12) received a high-calorie diet containing 17% animal fat and 17% fructose, with a total energy value of 4400 kcal/kg, which was used to induce a model of metabolic syndrome.

The correction group (n = 12), after 12 weeks of metabolic syndrome induction, was switched to a standard diet. To increase physical activity, the animals were housed in larger cages, and black grape juice was administered instead of drinking water, according to the methodology described by Santos Lacerda et al.

Study results: In recent decades, the global scientific literature has extensively described various approaches to the correction of metabolic syndrome and different degrees of obesity. The fundamental principle in correcting such pathological conditions should be directed toward their underlying causes and mechanisms. Numerous studies have demonstrated that therapeutic strategies targeting the etiology and pathogenesis of metabolic syndrome yield more effective outcomes.

Metabolic syndrome encompasses a cluster of disorders affecting carbohydrate and lipid metabolism. From the perspective of carbohydrate metabolism, it includes type 2 diabetes mellitus, hyperglycemia, and increased insulin resistance. In terms of lipid metabolism, it is associated with cardiovascular diseases such as arterial hypertension, ischemic heart disease, myocardial infarction, and stroke. Additionally, it contributes to decreased immune system activity, increased inflammatory processes, and a higher incidence of neoplastic diseases, all of which remain a major concern for healthcare professionals.

At the beginning of the experiment, the average body weight of animals in the control group was approximately 90 g, increasing to 235 g after 24 weeks, representing a 2.6-fold increase due to normal growth and development. In contrast, rats with an induced metabolic syndrome model reached an average body weight of 385 g, corresponding to a 4.3-fold increase from baseline and a 16.5% higher value compared to the control group.

In the correction group, body weight reached 295 g after 12 weeks of intervention, which is 3.3 times higher than the initial value but 1.3 times lower than that observed in untreated animals with metabolic syndrome.

At the end of the experimental period, the amount of visceral adipose tissue in rats with metabolic syndrome reached 5.1 g, representing a 2.8-fold increase compared to baseline and a 21.5% increase relative to the control group. In the correction group, visceral fat increased by 1.7 times compared to the initial level but was 1.7 times lower than in the untreated metabolic syndrome group.

The average liver weight in the control group increased from 2.2 g at baseline to 2.8 g at the end of the experiment (a 1.3-fold increase). In rats with metabolic syndrome, liver weight reached 3.8 g, corresponding to a 1.7-fold increase from baseline and a 13.6% increase compared to controls. In the correction group, liver weight was 3.2 g at the end of the experiment, representing a 1.45-fold increase from baseline but a 12% decrease compared to the untreated metabolic syndrome group.

Following the application of corrective interventions—including increased physical activity, dietary modification, and antioxidant exposure—morphological and functional changes were observed in the structures of the small intestinal wall. In the corrected animals, the small intestine retained its typical four-layered organization, including the mucosal, submucosal, muscular, and serosal layers.

Fig. 1. Small Intestinal Wall in the Correction Group

In the correction group, the epithelial layer of the small intestinal mucosa had an average thickness of $12.8 \pm 0.28 \mu\text{m}$. Goblet and endocrine cells within the villi gradually increased in number toward the crypts. The lamina propria of the mucosa consisted of loosely arranged connective tissue, with an average thickness of $23.1 \pm 0.74 \mu\text{m}$. Blood vessels, lymphatic vessels, and nerve fibers were distributed among the fibers of the lamina propria.

Fig. 2. Layers of the Small Intestinal Wall in the Correction Group

In the correction group, the total thickness of the small intestinal mucosa averaged $55.55 \pm 1.76 \mu\text{m}$. The submucosal layer of the small intestinal wall in corrected animals was composed of loosely arranged connective tissue. Within this layer, all types of connective tissue cells were present, along with collagen fibers, blood vessels of varying sizes, and lymph nodes. A mild increase in edema, lymphocytes, and macrophages within the tissue was observed, contributing to a slight thickening of the submucosa, with an average thickness of $18.2 \pm 1.26 \mu\text{m}$.

The muscular layer of the small intestinal wall in the experimental animals consisted of smooth muscle fibers oriented in both circular and longitudinal directions.

In the correction group, the total thickness of the small intestinal wall averaged $126.45 \pm 5.28 \mu\text{m}$, of which 43.9% corresponded to the mucosal layer, 14.4% to the submucosa, 33.3% to the muscular layer, and 8.4% to the serosal layer.

Fig. 3. Muscular and Outer Serosal Layers of the Small Intestinal Wall in the Correction Group

Thus, the overall thickness of the small intestinal wall in corrected animals was 1.6% greater than that of the control group, but 2.7% lower compared to animals with experimentally induced metabolic syndrome.

Conclusion: In experimental animals with an induced model of metabolic syndrome, significant morphological changes were observed in the small intestinal wall compared to the control group. These included thickening of the intestinal layers, increased density of villi and crypts, and enlargement of lymphoid nodules, reflecting the inflammatory processes occurring in the affected organs.

Application of a combined correction strategy—comprising dietary modification, increased physical activity, and antioxidant supplementation—resulted in a positive dynamic of morphological, morphometric, and functional parameters in the small intestinal wall. These improvements were associated with enhanced innervation, peristalsis, absorption, and secretory function, as well as a reduction in tissue edema, cellular infiltration, and other markers of inflammation, indicating restoration of intestinal structure and function.

In particular, animals receiving black grape juice as part of the corrective intervention demonstrated pronounced positive changes in small intestinal morphology and function, providing evidence of overall organ and systemic recovery.

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